

improved cultivars and other cultural practices were followed for the different crops. A minimum 7 d was taken between crops for field preparation.

Highest total yields, net returns, and

benefit:cost ratio were with rice - radish - onion, followed by rice - radish - vegetable pea - french bean. Rice - wheat had the lowest yields and net returns.

Protein, carbohydrates, fats, and energy

yields were highest with rice - radish - vegetable pea - french bean, rice - rapeseed *Brassica campestris* var. *toria* - potato/ cabbage, rice - radish - potato, and rice - radish - onion (see table). □

Production efficiency of rice-based crop sequences under irrigated upland conditions. UPKAS, Uttar Pradesh, India, 1982-85.

Crop sequence ^a	Yield (t/ha)	Total variable cost (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	Benefit:cost ratio	Protein (t/ha)	Carbohydrate (t/ha)	Fat (t/ha)	Energy (kcal × 10 ³ /ha)
1. Rice (VL 8)	4.6	514	506	2.0	0.8	0.09	6.7	31,073
Wheat (CPAN 1796)	4.4							
2. Rice (VL 8)	4.7	877	716	1.8	0.7	0.05	9.1	39,364
Potato	23.8							
3. Rice (VLK39)	3.8	1061	849	1.8	0.9	0.6	8.6	43,727
Rapeseed	1.5							
Potato	23.4							
4. Rice (VL 8)	4.7	1057	951	1.9	0.9	0.08	10.0	42,964
Radish	22.5							
Potato	23.7							
5. Rice (VLK39)	3.8	1286	1086	1.8	1.1	0.07	9.3	42,189
Cabbage	23.5							
Potato	23.5							
6. Rice (VLK39)	3.8	862	664	1.8	0.9	0.6	4.3	26,361
Rapeseed	1.4							
Cabbage	20.9							
7. Rice (VLK39)	3.7	1056	2215	3.1	1.1	0.1	9.8	44,233
Radish	31.3							
Onion (VL 67)	52.3							
8. Rice (VLK39)	3.8	694	613	1.9	0.9	0.1	6.4	30,059
Radish	24.4							
Wheat (Sonalika)	3.7							
9. Rice (VLK39)	3.8	1072	1367	2.3	1.8	0.07	7.0	35,780
Radish	23.2							
Vegetable bean (Arkel)	16.6							
French bean (VL 1)	12.9							

^aPotato variety was Kufri Jyoti; radish, Jap. White Long; cabbage, Golden Acre; rapeseed, T9.

Piara sowing of rabi pulses after rice at South Coastal Orissa, India

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Farmers have difficulty engaging enough bullock and farm power to undertake tillage of rabi pulses because power remains engaged for postharvest processing of rice. Timely seeding of rabi pulses should take advantage of field moisture. We evaluated

broadcasting of rabi pulses in ricefields before or soon after harvest (piara cultivation).

Four rabi pulses, cowpea C-152, green gram Berhampur local, black gram Sarala, and chickpea (local) were sown in a randomized block design with 4 replications during 1987-88 dry season on a plot where rice IR36 was grown during 1987-88 wet season with 60-20-20 kg NPK/ha. Pulse seeds were broadcast into standing rice (M₁) 1 wk before harvest, and in a separate plot soon after harvest (M₂). Soil was sandy loam with 6.1 pH, 0.38% organic C, 16 kg Olsen's P, and 305 kg available K/ ha.

There were no significant differences in yield and yield characters between M₁ and M₂ because there was adequate soil moisture for germination and growth. Cowpea had highest seed yield, closely followed by black gram. Green gram yield was lowest. Chickpea plants remained stunted because of low root growth and they failed to bear any pod. Cowpea was free from disease and pests. Green gram had severe infection of powdery mildew, with less on black gram and chickpea. Leaf beetles affected all pulses at seedling and vegetative growth phases. □